

ERROR AND MESSAGE DIALOGS

Content Usability Guidelines

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Foreword to the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative

The following document has been developed by the Error Messages Working Group of the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative (RO-SSI). The goal of the stakeholders group is to improve patient safety in radiation oncology. The RO-SSI meets twice a year (at the AAPM and ASTRO Annual Meetings). These meetings are attended by therapists, dosimetrists, medical physicists, biomedical and software engineers, clinical application experts, physicians, and therapy product manufacturers' experts. The attendees are affiliated with hospital-based or free standing radiation therapy departments, radiation therapy product manufacturers, regulatory agencies, independent physician and physicist practices as well as manufacturers' associations, professional associations and societies.

The purpose of the Safety Stakeholder's Initiative is to combine the expertise of all stakeholders to identify opportunities for improving patient safety in all aspects of the radiation therapy treatment process. The RO-SSI, which is independent from all other organizations, develops recommendations for consideration by the various entities with responsibilities for all or part of the radiation therapy treatment process.

In order to focus on various phases, functions and areas of the treatment process, the RO-SSI has organized several Working Groups (WGs) to concentrate on particular issues and eventually prepare recommendations. The recommendations represent the consensus of the members of the working groups. It should be noted that members of the working groups are individual expert contributors and their consent to a recommendation does not necessarily

represent the endorsement of their employers.

The intent of the RO-SSI is to advise and suggest rather than prescribe actions or processes. It is hoped that the various organizations and societies with authority and responsibility in radiation oncology will consider the initiative's recommendations as they impact the respective roles of the existing organizations. Organizations which agree with RO-SSI recommendations will be able to post their support for the document as well as implement its use in their own environments. Through this open and transparent process, all radiation oncology professionals will have the opportunity to recognize and make use of the recommendations which have been developed by this unique and independent group of vendors, clinical users and other stakeholders.

GOALS

The main goals of this document are to describe the best practices and design guidelines for message dialogs, and to illustrate these with specific examples from the field of radiation oncology. Making message dialogs in radiotherapy software and hardware products intelligible and actionable are important for assuring safe patient treatment.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

In many instances, message dialogs are poorly written and therefore not very useful or worse, can be misinterpreted or ignored by the user with the potential for improper use of the system and even patient harm . Potential root causes of the problem are:

Message dialogs are designed from the point of view of the manufacturer's developers and not that of the clinical users.

Message dialogs are often written with little input from therapists, physicists and service engineers.

The developers may not have been trained in the best practices for writing message dialogs, and they may not have been encouraged to review their products with clinical experts.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

Vendors' engineering department members including software engineers, quality assurance engineers and technical writers.

Usability and human factors engineers.

Marketing representatives (e.g.: product managers, business analysts).

BASIC STRUCTURE

Error Messages

Effective error messages should contain the following elements:

The **problem** that has occurred

The **cause** of the problem

The **solution** to enable users to fix or otherwise appropriately react to the problem.

Correct Example:

“The selected plans cannot be summed because their dose calculation boxes do not overlap. Enlarge the dose calculation boxes in each plan.”

The above example tells the users what happened (problem), why the problem happened (cause), and what to do to fix it or prevent it from happening again (solution).

Note that in certain instances, a system designer cannot tell what exactly has caused the error state. In these edge cases, the error message will only indicate the problem and the solution.

Warning Messages

Compelling warnings contain the following elements:

Source of the warning (e.g. changed settings, disk almost full, not all parameters needed are set in a panel)

The **potential problem** that might occur.

What the user might choose to do about it.

A special case of warning messages are confirmations that the user wants to proceed with an action that has potential risks. Note that such messages will also contain a question to determine if the user wants to proceed.

SIX BEST PRACTICES FOR MESSAGE DIALOGS

In this section we summarize the six main guidelines for appropriate message dialogs based on the [Windows User Experience \(UX\) Interaction Guidelines \(1\)](#).

1. User Centered

Use language that is easily understood by the user, in the context of the problem, i.e. describe the problem in terms of user actions or goals, not in programmer’s terminology.

Avoid technical jargon. Do not use actual source code language, internal messages, and variable names.

This message is written completely in technical jargon and conveys no useful information to the user.

Use the table below as a reference to help you replace engineering jargon or overly-strong verbiage with plain language.

Instead of	Use
error, failure	problem
failed to	unable
illegal, invalid, bad	incorrect
abort, kill, terminate	stop
catastrophic, fatal	serious
destroy	remove

Table Source: Adapted from Windows UX Guidelines (1)

2. Clear

Use plain language so that users can easily understand the problem and the solution. A helpful message quickly steers the users to the correct solution.

Incorrect message: The word 'select' is used in three different ways in one short sentence making the message confusing. It is hard for users to understand what action they need to take.

Always use complete sentences, with the basic structure of subject, verb and object.

Avoid acronyms and abbreviations. An unfamiliar acronym will confuse a user, and abruptly

stop the flow of communication.

Incorrect message: The user might not be familiar with the two acronyms listed in the dialog.

Be consistent in style, language, and format. Inconsistency can compromise clarity and understanding, and may lead to doubt in the reader’s mind about the accuracy and reliability of the information. Use words and phrases consistently, e.g. use “Couch Rotation” all the time, instead of switching between “Couch Rtn”, “CouchAng” or “CouchRot”.

3. Actionable

Users should be able to either perform an action, or change their work process, as the result of the message. Use different messages for different detectable causes. Some well designed messages are accompanied by an action from the software itself. For example, first the message tells the user how to fix the problem, and then, upon acknowledging the message, the user is automatically placed in the correct window to do so.

Note: Recommending contacting technical support is rarely necessary. The option is always available, and doesn’t need to be promoted through messages.

4. Concise

Convey to the user the essential information concisely. Keep the message short by deleting unnecessary words and sentences.

Use the keywords early in your message. In many instances users simply scan the text of a message and some won’t read the text at all. Thus, it is important to introduce the essential message quickly. Progressive disclosure and Help Links can be used to provide additional information.

Remove redundant text: look for it in titles, main instructions, command links and main buttons. Generally leave full text in instructions and interactive controls, and remove redundancy from the other places.

5. Specific

The message should describe the problem, giving specific names, locations, and values of the components involved. Write exactly what the user needs to know, using words with precise meanings and including details that are directly relevant.

Incorrect message: The user is not told the name and location of the file and what are the steps to solve the problem.

6. Courteous

The message should be polite, without implying blame or wrongful act. In a sense, an error message reflects a failure of the program in facilitating the user in his/her task.

Note: Windows UX Interaction Guidelines (1) , for message dialogs recommend that the word “Please” is used only for situation when the user is asked to wait for the computer to perform an action.

Note: Don’t use the ‘OK’ control label for error messages since this implies that problems are OK. Use “Close” instead.

PROGRESSIVE DISCLOSURE

Use a Show/Hide Details progressive disclosure button to hide advanced or detailed information in an error message. Doing so may simplify the message, but has the risk of hiding needed information. Thus, the pro and con must be balanced.

Don’t use Show/Hide details unless there is incremental detail, and not a verbose restatement of the same information.

ERROR CODES

For situations where specific and actionable error messages are not possible, consider providing error codes for which additional information is available in “Help”.

Assign a unique error code for each different cause. Doing so makes troubleshooting much more straightforward as it provides specific information about the problem.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

All new message dialogs should go through an internal review process with clinical experts. The goal is to ensure clarity and consistency, and as a safeguard for potential problems in clinical implementation.

The clinical experts should understand the context, situations, and conditions pertaining to the error messages they are reviewing.

This user-based review should occur as early as possible and clinical input should be ongoing throughout the software development.

VISUAL DESIGN GUIDELINES

Make good use of white space. Do not cram the text and controls in a small box frame.

To improve readability, avoid using the maximum width for text boxes. Wrap the text to keep text boxes at a visually digestible size for the reader.

Use consistent type size and color for messages with the same severity. Multiple levels of severity should be demonstrated by different and consistent text type and colors.

Use consistent icons (see Terminology document).

Do not display entire words or sentences in capital letters. Always use sentence style capitalization.

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APPENDIX 1

Following internal training to software engineering groups, vendors should distribute a copy of the checklist below to each developer, engineer or any other staff member involved in drafting message dialogs so it can be used as a quick and easy reference for good usability practices.

CHECKLIST – Message Dialogs Guidelines

User Centered

Avoid technical jargon. Ask for clinical feedback early on.

Clear

Plain language

Complete sentences

Avoid acronyms

Do not imply that the system can feel

Use words consistently

Actionable

Provide a solution

Specific

Indicate names, locations or values

Concise

As brief as possible

Clinically Reviewed

Ask clinical user representatives for feedback

APPENDIX 2

The following examples are all real message dialogs from radiation oncology applications. The authors of this report have put the messages in a generic visual display but preserved the actual content. The intent was not to single out particular products but to illustrate the guidelines and create an educational tool for engineering training materials.

Incorrect Message Examples from the Radiation Oncology Field

Technical jargon

Use of acronyms and exclamation mark

Error is not OK

Not actionable

Technical jargon

Use of acronyms and exclamation mark

Error is not OK

Not actionable

Unintelligible

Misunderstanding of the word discontinued

Inappropriate message if read by patient

Technical Jargon

Error is not OK

Not actionable

Uses acronyms

Is this a crucial dosimetry error or a minor problem?

Not specific or actionable

Does not use a complete sentence

Technical jargon

Error is not OK

Confusing message

Scope of error is not clear, nor is the freedom of the user to respond in multiple ways.
The implication of each option should be spelled out clearly.

Technical jargon

Error is not OK

Should be actionable – what characters that were entered are wrong – how does the user correct the entry?

Technical jargon

Sentence in caps lock and exclamation points

Inconsistent use of decimal points.

Importance of error, and the reason it happened (understandable by the user) are not described.

What is the correct user response – how do they fix this?

Implies the system can make think and make decisions

What was the error, and how important is it?

Does the user need to do something next, or will the shut down happen on its own?

Not actionable. Missing the 'Yes' button.

Technical jargon

No description of what changed

Not specific. "Some ROI" – the system should describe which ROI is a problem, and why.
Not suitable" – in what way?

Not actionable. "Continue anyway" – What will happen then?

Technical jargon

Error is not OK

Not actionable

Better:

An error was found in the DICOM information that is needed to treat this patient.
Acknowledge and then restart the program and if that does not resolve the problem,
restart the computer.

Technical jargon

Error is not OK

Uses acronyms

Not actionable

Technical jargon

Error is not OK

Uses acronyms

More specificity needed – which images need to be saved, and how is that done?

Technical jargon

Not concise

Cause not clear

Appropriate user response not described

Better message: "An error occurred during the loading of the treatment fields. This may be due to a database error or a network communication error. After acknowledging, try to reload the plan."

Uses acronyms

Uses caps lock

Technical jargon

Better message: "There is incorrect data for the following treatment fields: list the fields. The couch longitudinal value is either missing or out of range. Correct these values and re-load the plan."

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